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PREDICTIVE MODELLING AND ANALYSIS OF SOILING LOSSES IN PV PLANTS THROUGH A HYBRID DATA-DRIVEN APPROACH

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ABSTRACT: Photovoltaic (PV) system efficiency is significantly affected by soiling, leading to energy losses and increased operational costs. Within the SERENDI-PV project, this study refines soiling loss modeling through two complementary approaches: the Stochastic Quantifying Soiling Loss (SQL) method and a machine learning (ML)-based predictive model. SQL quantifies soiling losses using electrical performance data, independent of meteorological inputs, while the ML model forecasts losses using environmental parameters such as temperature, humidity, wind speed, and particulate matter concentration. The SQL method identifies soiling phases—cleaning periods, stable periods, and soiling periods—by analyzing PV performance trends. Monte Carlo simulations generate probable soiling profiles, assessing uncertainty and informing maintenance strategies. Additionally, SQL enables classification of soiling accumulation patterns, distinguishing between gradual and rapid soiling events. The ML-based approach integrates artificial neural networks and regression models to predict soiling losses, applying data pre-processing techniques to enhance accuracy. Regional climate variations and site-specific soiling characteristics are incorporated to improve predictive performance. Preliminary results validate the robustness of both methodologies. SQL-generated profiles align closely with observed soiling trends, and ML models effectively capture seasonal variations. Field studies at a utility-scale PV plant in Spain further demonstrate the location dependency of soiling patterns. Comparative analysis of SQL predictions and real soiling measurements shows prediction errors between 1% and 2.6% over an eight-day forecast period. These findings support the integration of predictive soiling models into PV monitoring platforms, optimizing maintenance strategies and minimizing energy yield losses.

Keywords: *PV systems; soiling loss modeling; machine learning (ML); PV performance, predictive modelling.*

1 INTRODUCTION: CONTEXT and AIM

Soiling, the accumulation of dust and particulate matter on photovoltaic (PV) modules, is a major factor in system performance degradation, causing significant energy losses and elevating operational expenses [1-3]. This makes its management crucial for optimizing PV output. As detailed in [1], research into soiling has evolved to encompass various assessment methods and mitigation strategies, including cleaning and anti-soiling coatings. The review in [2] emphasizes the severity of soiling losses in arid and polluted regions, noting the benefits of passive anti-soiling coatings—such as waterless operation, lower cost, and durability—over active cleaning methods. Furthermore, Bess et al. in [3] stress the importance of site-specific monitoring, evaluate different sensor technologies, and predict a rising global demand for thousands of sensors annually, while also providing economic analysis and experimental comparisons of mitigation techniques.

The economic impact is substantial, with global income losses from soiling-induced degradation estimated to surpass 10 billion EUR per year [4]. The severity of soiling is influenced by a combination of factors: local climate (rainfall, wind speed, humidity), airborne particulate composition (PM10, PM2.5), and site-specific conditions like proximity to deserts or urban areas. Consequently, soiling loss estimates vary widely, underscoring the necessity for accurate quantification, modeling, and prediction to optimize cleaning schedules, enhance energy yield forecasts, and enable proactive maintenance [5-7]. Experts from IEA PVPS Task 13, in both [5] and [6], have comprehensively summarized

soiling, covering global dust distribution, particle types, measurement techniques, modeling, economic impacts, and mitigation strategies—including climate-specific maintenance and considerations for snow in higher latitudes. Meanwhile, the researchers in [7] developed innovative, calibration-free testing prototypes for accurate power loss estimation and provided new insights into soiling mechanisms through a lab protocol.

Accurately assessing soiling remains complex. Many existing models are validated on data from specific locations, raising concerns about their generalizability to diverse climates and sites. The dynamic nature of soiling, driven by multiple interacting environmental factors, demands robust modeling techniques capable of capturing these intricate relationships [8-9].

Soiling modeling approaches fall into three main categories: analytical/physics-based, empirical/statistical, and data-driven models. Analytical models use mathematical formulas with environmental data like rainfall and particulate matter concentration to estimate losses. A more detailed subset, physics-based models, simulate the fundamental mechanisms of dust deposition and removal by incorporating factors such as particle size, wind, and humidity.

One of the simplest analytical models is by Kimber [10], which assumes linear accumulation during dry periods and complete cleaning after a fixed rainfall threshold. However, it doesn't account for particulate matter concentration or partial cleaning. More advanced models address these limitations. The Humboldt State University (HSU) model [11] incorporates PM10/PM2.5 concentration, deposition velocity, and tilt angle. Toth et al. [12] proposed a model that differentiates between fine

and coarse particles, better capturing the adhesive properties of fine dust. A comparative analysis on Spanish PV plants [13] found the Kimber model to be the simplest but least accurate. The HSU and Toth models improved accuracy by including particulate matter but were still limited by fixed thresholds. The SOMOSclean model [13] demonstrated the best performance with a mean absolute error of 0.694%; it uses an exponential growth function to simulate saturation and variable rainfall cleaning thresholds. A key limitation of physics-based models is their high demand for extensive, site-specific environmental and dust property data.

Empirical and statistical models use historical performance data to quantify losses. A standard method is the Soiling Ratio (SR), which compares a soiled module to a clean reference [7]. Other methods calculate a dirt derating factor [14] or analyze performance trends to infer soiling rates [15,16]. While straightforward, their accuracy can be compromised if a reliable clean reference is unavailable or if clean periods cannot be precisely identified.

The rise of large datasets has accelerated the use of machine learning (ML) models for soiling prediction. These data-driven methods excel at identifying complex, non-linear patterns that are difficult for traditional models to capture. Common techniques include linear regression and artificial neural networks (ANNs), with ANNs often delivering superior results. For instance, Laarabi et al. [17] and Chiteka et al. [18] used ANNs with environmental variables like rainfall and humidity to predict losses, showing improved accuracy despite being constrained by data availability and computational demands. Zitouni et al. [19] combined ML with regression, underscoring the potential of hybrid approaches. A notable data-driven method is the Stochastic Rate and Recovery (SRR) technique, which automatically detects soiling and cleaning events and models rates from a single system's data without a clean reference [15].

Research highlights the value of using hourly data to capture intra-day variations and training models over long periods to identify seasonal patterns. Common inputs include ambient temperature, relative humidity, wind, rainfall, particulate matter, and system tilt to extract "PV soiling profiles" for analysis, forecasting, and optimized cleaning [20]. Data processing involves standardization, cleaning, and filtering for specific conditions like snow. A recognized limitation is that many ML models are trained on data from a single location, underscoring the need for multi-environment training to improve generalizability. Future research directions include exploring advanced neural networks (e.g., Time-Series, Recurrent Neural Networks) and integrating considerations for bifacial PV systems.

Significant recent advancements have been made in soiling characterization and forecasting. Micheli et al. [20] created a framework for generating site-specific soiling profiles, showing that median-based annualized rates often miss seasonal variations. Their weighted average and Markov-chain algorithms achieved prediction errors below 1.3% and could identify optimal cleaning dates within three weeks, a major improvement over conventional methods. Kumar et al. [21] advanced empirical modeling by testing five variants of the Kimber and HSU models against sensor data. Their optimized models reduced RMSE by up to 23%, with all configurations keeping MAPE under 1%. They found that modified Kimber models excelled during extended dry

periods and frequent rainfall, while their adapted HSU model was 12% more accurate than the original, highlighting the need for site-specific model selection based on local precipitation.

Alternative prediction methods have also emerged. Ballestrín et al. [22] showed the efficacy of ARMA time-series models, achieving a mean relative error of just 0.07% for seasonal forecasts, though they were less effective at predicting daily fluctuations. Smestad et al. [23] and Micheli et al. [24] pioneered spectral and image analysis techniques, respectively. In [23], researchers established that natural soiling follows consistent transmittance patterns and provided a cross-validation framework linking cleanliness standards to optical measurements ($R^2 = 0.89$). Meanwhile, work in [24] investigated image analysis thresholding uncertainties on a large micrograph dataset, finding methods like "percentile" and bimodal distributions to be inconsistent. They identified the "Triangle" method as the most reliable and recommended multiple micrographs per sample to account for non-uniformity and keep error low. The convergence of optical [23,24], statistical [22], and machine-learning enhanced [21] approaches points toward a new multi-method paradigm for soiling assessment.

Despite progress, challenges remain, including the incomplete integration of variables like wind and humidity, and sensor limitations. ML models require large datasets, restricting their use in data-sparse regions. Within the SERENDI-PV project, this study aims to refine soiling loss modeling and create predictive tools to enhance maintenance and yield forecasting. We present two complementary approaches: the Stochastic Quantifying Soiling Loss (SQL) method for retrospective analysis from performance data, and a machine learning-based model for forward-looking predictions using environmental data. The ultimate goal is to integrate these into predictive tools for improved energy yield assessments, enabling data-driven decisions to minimize soiling-related losses.

2 METHODOLOGY – APPROACH

The SQL method identifies soiling trends by analyzing PV performance metrics over time. Unlike traditional methods that require external environmental inputs such as rainfall data, SQL relies entirely on variations in electrical performance, making it particularly useful in cases where meteorological data is unavailable or unreliable. In such approach, statistical thresholds are defined to segment performance variations into distinct "key" phases that make up the soiling profile: cleaning periods (CP), stable periods (StP), and soiling periods (SoP). Cleaning events are identified based on a significant increase in PV performance metrics, while stable periods are detected by analyzing fluctuations within a defined threshold. The transition into a soiling period is determined once PV performance metrics imply degradation beyond acceptable variation limits. A *theoretical* representation of these different phases is given in Fig. 1 (top), illustrating the transitions between cleaning, stable, and soiling periods. To contextualize such phases/classifications into real-life profiles of soiling losses, Fig. 1 (bottom) shows an example profile from *actual* real-case data, displaying how these phases are detected in practice.

We employ statistical analyses and Monte Carlo

simulations, to generate *probable* soiling profiles, enabling estimates of average soiling ratios and uncertainty ranges. This probabilistic approach helps define different soiling scenarios, ranging from worst-case to optimal conditions. The methodology also includes sensitivity analysis, examining how variations in input parameters, such as the frequency and effectiveness of cleaning events, influence the estimated soiling losses. Additionally, the SQL method allows the classification of different soiling accumulation patterns by analyzing the rate of PV performance decline during soiling periods. This enables distinguishing between slow, gradual soiling accumulation and rapid degradation due to specific environmental conditions. Such “soiling profiling” capability provides valuable insights for optimizing maintenance strategies for PV plants.

Figure 1: Top: Theoretical representation of the different key phases-variations in PV performance, considered for soiling profiling in the SQL approach. Bottom: Identification of such phases within a real-case performance/soiling data from a utility-scale PV plant.

A complementary machine learning (ML)-based methodology (Fig. 2) integrates artificial neural networks and regression models to predict soiling losses from environmental parameters. These models process historical data, applying rigorous pre-processing steps such as data standardization, outlier removal, and missing data correction. The inclusion of wind speed, rainfall (precipitation) accumulation, and particulate matter levels improves model accuracy. A filtering process refines environmental datasets, correcting anomalies in precipitation records based on correlated meteorological variables, thereby ensuring better soiling loss estimations. Additionally, the developed methodology accounts for site-specific soiling characteristics by incorporating long-term data analysis. Soiling accumulation patterns vary significantly based on regional climate, local air pollution levels, and seasonal effects. The study emphasizes the importance of adapting soiling models to local conditions

to improve predictive accuracy. To exclude snowy days from soiling ratio calculations, as also shown in Fig. 2, a filter is applied based on snow depth and albedo measurements. Since snow depth sensors can be noisy, only days with a significant albedo increase are considered snowy.

Figure 2: Architecture of the ML-based model for soiling loss prediction, assessed complementarily in this study.

3 RESULTS and DISCUSSION

Preliminary SQL validation results indicate a high correlation between simulated and actual soiling profiles. The Monte Carlo-generated profiles effectively reconstruct historical soiling trends, confirming the robustness of the method. Figure 3 demonstrates this through a set of simulated PV performance (soiling loss) profiles, for the real-case study data of Fig.1-right, illustrating how uncertainty ranges are captured in the estimation. The post-cleaning PV performance jumps observed in field data validate the method’s ability to estimate cleaning efficiencies under different operational conditions.

Figure 3: Example results of SQL-based generation of various soiling loss profiles, based on the real-case data/curve shown in Fig.1.

Further, the ML-based models trained on datasets from NREL and CEA floating PV plant demonstrate a strong ability to capture seasonal soiling variations. The comparison of measured and predicted soiling ratios (Fig. 4) reveals that prolonged training periods improve predictive accuracy. However, the models require further refinement to account for location-specific environmental influences.

Further simulations, employing both our SQL method and our ML modelling framework, were carried out for the case of a utility-scale PV plant located in the Aragon region, northeastern Spain. The studied PV installation, with installed capacity of 62 MW_p, spans over 100 ha in a soiling prone site, influenced by climatic conditions (cold semi-arid climate (BSk)) that favor dust

accumulations. In the specific case, for employing the SQL approach, we examined DC current measurements at PV strings level, for a full year, identifying different soiling periods based on performance output (PV production) patterns. Different PV string locations experience distinct soiling behaviors due to varying micro-climatic exposure conditions. Figure 5 presents indicative examples of resulting soiling profiles, generated through distinct “training”, “validation” and “test” data. The modelling results are suggestive of considerable variations across soiling profiles for different strings, highlighting the location-dependency and influence of microclimatic conditions on soiling losses, particularly in the case of wide-area soiling-prone PV installations.

Figure 4: Top: Measured soiling ratio for the case of NREL dataset, over a 7-year period (01/2010-01/2017). Bottom: Measured vs. predicted (through the CEA ML-based model) soiling ratio, over two years (01/2013-01/2015) of the same NREL dataset.

Although the SQL method does not rely on weather data as inputs for its computations, environmental parameters such as wind speed, humidity, and precipitation were analyzed to validate and interpret the soiling trends observed in the electrical data. This auxiliary analysis helps confirm whether environmental conditions align with SQL-detected cleaning and soiling events. For instance, the correlation between increased humidity and dust adhesion, or the impact of heavy rainfall on natural cleaning, provides insights into the accuracy of SQL-based estimations.

Finally, Fig. 6 presents example comparative results on the soiling ratio predicted (8 days ahead) by applying the SQL method against actual soiling ratio measurements, for an indicative period of 3 months in 2024, for four different PV strings of the aforementioned PV plant. In this case, prediction errors range between 1% and 2.6%. Despite the short period of the training dataset (from 20/03/2023 to 05/03/2024), the results are encouraging. This limited period of measurement does not allow the model to learn much of the tendency in the long term, but the errors observed are sufficiently low to consider a reliable prediction/simulation of soiling losses in such real-life cases

Figure 5: Soiling rate trends for different PV strings (three indicative examples) of the studied utility-scale PV plant in northeastern Spain. Labels 'train,' 'validation,' and 'test' indicate the data split used for model training and evaluation.

Next to the presented predictive modelling framework for PV soiling losses, CEA has also developed a virtual case study generator to support further soiling model development. This tool – which will be discussed in more details in the full version of this paper – simulates daily soiling rates based on multivariable regression models, considering wind speed, rainfall, and airborne dust concentration. It generates synthetic datasets useful for validating and improving soiling models under controlled conditions. The ability to predict daily soiling ratios provides valuable insights for optimizing maintenance strategies.

Further investigation reveals that soiling losses exhibit non-linear degradation patterns, influenced by meteorological anomalies. Periods of high relative humidity combined with low wind speeds create conditions that promote dust adhesion, significantly increasing soiling rates. Conversely, heavy precipitation events can lead to unexpected recovery in performance.

Figure 6: ML-based predictive modelling of the soiling ratio (SR) for four different PV strings of the studied PV plant in northeastern Spain: Comparative results of predicted SR vs real SR, 8-days ahead prediction, for a study period of 3 months.

4 CONCLUSIONS - OUTLOOK

The field of PV soiling modeling and prediction is rapidly evolving in response to the urgent need to mitigate energy losses and enhance operational efficiency. This study contributes to this objective by introducing two synergistic methodologies: the Stochastic Quantifying Soiling Loss (SQLS) method and a machine learning (ML)-based predictive model. Both approaches are designed for integration into existing PV monitoring platforms to refine maintenance planning and reduce energy yield degradation.

The SQLS method offers a robust framework for retrospective analysis, quantifying soiling impacts using exclusively electrical performance data, without dependence on external meteorological inputs. By examining performance trends, the method identifies and categorizes key soiling phases—such as cleaning intervals, stable performance periods, and soiling accumulation periods. Utilizing Monte Carlo simulations, it generates probabilistic soiling profiles that estimate average soiling ratios and associated uncertainty ranges. This stochastic methodology supports the definition of diverse soiling scenarios, from worst-case degradation to optimal conditions, thereby offering critical insights for maintenance optimization. It further enables the classification of accumulation patterns, distinguishing between gradual soiling buildup and rapid performance decline. Initial validation confirms the robustness of the SQLS approach, with generated profiles showing strong alignment with empirical observations. In field testing at a utility-scale PV plant in Spain, the model achieved soiling ratio predictions up to eight days in advance, with errors between 1% and 2.6%. Although currently focused on retrospective analysis, future development aims to incorporate weather forecasts and seasonal priors into the Monte Carlo simulations, enhancing predictive capability and improving the representation of seasonal variability for more reliable cleaning scheduling.

Complementing the SQLS method, the ML-based predictive model employs a forward-looking approach, leveraging an extensive set of environmental parameters. This model integrates artificial neural networks and regression techniques, augmented with advanced data pre-processing, to capture complex non-linear relationships and seasonal dynamics often missed by conventional models. Trained on hourly data over extended periods, the model accommodates regional climate variations and site-specific soiling behaviors, improving predictive accuracy. Validation using datasets from NREL and a CEA floating PV installation demonstrated the model's capacity to predict seasonal soiling trends, with performance improving as training duration increases.

Despite these advances, several challenges persist. Many ML models remain constrained by limited generalizability, having been trained and validated on data from single locations. The substantial data requirements of powerful ML algorithms also restrict their applicability in regions with sparse monitoring infrastructure. Additionally, discrepancies between pyranometer-based soiling estimates and electrical performance-based quantifications underscore the need for multi-source validation to improve assessment robustness. Future efforts will focus on enhancing model adaptability across diverse environments, refining input parameters, and investigating advanced ML architectures such as Time-Series Neural Networks and Recurrent Neural Networks. Further development will include adaptation for bifacial PV systems and validation against measurements from a dedicated CEA soiling sensor. A virtual case study generator will also be employed to produce synthetic datasets under controlled conditions, supporting ongoing model validation and refinement.

By uniting these two methodologies, this research establishes a comprehensive and reliable framework to support PV plant operators in making data-informed decisions, ultimately improving economic efficiency and strategic operational planning.

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